

COMPREHENSIVE INVESTIGATION ON THERMAL DEGRADATION COMBINED EFFECTS IN AGED WOVEN CARBON FIBERS/EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Aging of polymer matrix composites is a complex combination of the actions of numerous parameters such as temperature, moisture, oxygen, pressure, radiations... This study is dealing with the consequences of long-time exposure of a carbon/epoxy composite to two penalizing factors, temperature and oxygen. Two different atmospheres, inert and oxidizing, are used in order to investigate separately heat and oxygen actions. To better understand thermo-oxidation mechanisms, a multi-holed laminate frequently used in aerospace industry is considered. First, to emphasize aging effects due to temperature and oxygen, thermal tests were carried out at T_g of the neat resin. Substantial damage by cracking and delamination is produced by different thermal expansion between fibers and matrix and masks each effect from all other implicated aging factors either under inert or oxidizing atmosphere. For isothermal conditions inside the glassy state although above use conditions, thermo-oxidation next to free surfaces and thermolysis effect in the bulk of the matrix are also implicated in degradation mechanisms. Weight losses, chemical modifications and developments of cracks were observed. Phenomenological aspects of different aging factors are discussed.

KEYWORDS : epoxy resin, aging, damage, cracking, oxidation, thermolysis, physical properties

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, composites are widely used in aerospace industry because of excellent mechanical properties combined with low weight. Nevertheless, under the action of various aging factors partly and previously examined such as temperature [1], humidity [2], oxygen [3], pressure [4]..., mechanical properties decrease, compromising the structure integrity [5, 6]. The knowledge on composite durability is therefore of a particular interest for industrial partners.

The aim of the studies on composite aging is to understand degradation mechanisms in order to predict laminate durability. However, the effects of the coupled aging parameters are really difficult to analyze and even for just one factor, the relationships between structure and properties are not yet fully understood. One way to overcome this would be to study the

influence of each individual parameter and then to combine them to approach the real solicitation. The most penalizing parameters for laminates have thus to be determined. In service-life, during flight level, thermo-structural composites evolve in air and are principally subjected to heat and oxidizing atmosphere. For flight level, moisture rate is very low and is therefore not a major parameter. In this context, temperature and oxygen are the main aging factors and their actions will be considered separately and in a combined manner.

For a better understanding of the relative actions of temperature and oxygen, plain and multi-holed composite panels have been studied. The approach presents an industrial interest since multi-holed composite panels are largely used in aerospace applications because of their acoustic properties.

MATERIALS AND INVESTIGATION METHODOLOGY

The studied material, a 8-ply composite regularly used in aerospace industry, consists of T300 woven fibers with an epoxy resin matrix. Exact composition of the epoxy resin is not known for commercial reasons but its main components are identified as two pre-polymers made of epoxy multi-functional (TGMDA and TGAP) mixed with an amino-hardener (DDA) and a plasticizer (PES). Prepegs are stacked in a quasi-isotropic sequence $[0/+45/-45/90]_s$, processed by autoclave at 180°C for one hour under 0.7 MPa and post-cured 4 hours at 190°C under atmospheric pressure. Two sorts of laminates are prepared, plain and multi-holed panels. There are about eight holes per square centimeter all over the surface of the perforated panels. The pattern of the holes is represented in Fig.1.

Figure 1 : Size and layout of holes in the composite laminate

To understand the composite evolution all along the aging, different kinds of characterization are used, such as weight loss measurements, Fourier Transformed InfraRed spectroscopy (FTIR), Dynamical Mechanical Analysis (DMA), Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (MDSC) and microscopic observations. It must be noticed that this work is not finished and that aging and characterization are still in progress:

- Weight loss measurements are performed regularly during aging. Samples are cooled down to room temperature before being weighed with a precision balance. Then, they are replaced in the ovens, the temperature rises again to the selected isotherm. Heating and cooling rates do not exceed $3^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to avoid introducing thermal shock effects.
- FTIR spectra are recorded every 500 hours on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One spectrometer, in reflection mode. A Perkin-Elmer AutoIMAGE microscope associated with the spectrometer allows to target the matrix between the fibers. Spectra are analyzed between 1750 and 700 cm^{-1} .
- MDSC samples are assessed on a TA Instruments 2920 calorimeter. Heating rate, frequency and amplitude of modulation applied are respectively $3^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, 1 Hz and $\pm 0,954^{\circ}\text{C}$. Three samples are tested for each panel.

- MDA experiments are conducted on a Metravib VA2000 analyser, in 3 points free flexion mode. For each panel, three samples are tested, with a heating rate of $3^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and a sollicitation frequency of 1 Hz. The glass transition temperature is taken at the maximum of the loss modulus (E'') curve.
- Microscopic observations are performed on a Leica DMLP optical microscope.

To better understand degradation mechanisms occurring in the laminate matrix, some experiments are conducted on neat resin. The resin has the same epoxy structure as the composite matrix and it has been cured and post-cured at the same temperatures.

INITIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The initial laminate characterization shows a healthy composite, without porosity or crack, as illustrated in Fig.2. The glass transition temperature, T_g , determined by MDA is 190°C . The FTIR spectrum shows some characteristic peaks which can be attributed to functional groups, in accordance with literature data [7, 8].

Figure 2 : Optical micrograph of the laminate in initial state

AGING CONDITIONS

As expected composite lifetime at use temperature is very long, it is not possible to study their degradation in real-time. Aging has therefore to be accelerated by raising temperature. The higher temperature is, the faster degradation will occur. The problem is that some modifications undergone by the material may not be the same when the aging temperature is too far from the use one.

In this work, different aging temperatures have been selected. A first part of the study consisted in placing composite and resin panels under severe conditions, above T_g of the matrix, precisely at 210°C , in order to emphasize damage effects. Three other temperatures below T_g but above the use temperature (120°C) are used, in order to study thermal aging under accelerated conditions next to the real ones (Fig.3).

Figure 3 : Location of aging temperatures relatively to the viscoelastic matrix properties

Aging time varies from a few days to more than one and a half year. Under extreme conditions, aging time lasted some hundred hours. Below T_g , it is carried on longer duration such as 9 000 hours (15 months) at 180°C, 12 000 hours (18 months) at 160°C and 15 000 hours (21 months) at 140°C.

To study consequences of heat alone, composite panels are aged under inert atmosphere, by using ovens under nitrogen or under vacuum. To investigate the coupled effects of temperature and oxygen, air-circulating ovens are used.

EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Neat resin aged at 210°C

Neat resin samples have been aged under extreme conditions, three in an oven under vacuum, three in an air-circulating oven for 700 hours. The initial glass transition temperature of the neat resin determined by MDA is 210°C, higher than T_g of the composite matrix because the neat resin is more reactive during its polymerization. The characterization after aging demonstrates that even under vacuum, epoxy resin undergoes some degradation of its network.

After aging under inert atmosphere, weight measurements show that the neat resin loses 5 % of its mass. The glass transition temperature, determined by MDA rises up to 227°C. No changes in the sample geometry can be observed and optical microscopy shows that material is undamaged, no crack, no oxidation layer can be observed.

After aging under oxidative atmosphere, weight loss is more important since the resin loses 12 % of its mass. The glass transition temperature is unchanged. In opposition to aging under vacuum, the sample geometry is modified and its dimensions are reduced. Moreover, the aspect of the surface is also altered. Surface has been completely smoothed, deleting all asperities. Resin degradation was observed by microscopy. A micrograph, obtained by interferential contrast on a failure section (Fig.4), highlights the oxidized outer layer (in black) and a ductile-brittle transition zone (light area) between the brittle oxidized layer and the

ductile intact core of the material (in gray). It can also be noticed that the corners of the sample are eroded.

Figure 4 : Optical micrograph of the resin aged for 700 hours at 210°C in air

Composite laminates aged at 210°C

Two laminate panels have been aged, under vacuum and under air, at 210°C for 200 hours. After aging, it can be seen that both composite panels have undergone severe and identical damages.

Microscopic examination shows that for both thermal and thermo-oxidative aging, the composite is extremely degraded. Interlaminar cracks and delaminations can be observed through the whole laminate (Fig.5). FTIR shows that the epoxy resin undergoes some chemical modifications. These changes are the same as those described in the following section.

Figure 5 : Optical micrograph of the composite aged for 200 hours at 210°C in air

Composite laminates aged below T_g

Different series of plain and multi-holed composite panels have been placed in nitrogen- or air-circulating ovens, at 140, 160 and 180°C. The aging duration have reached 2 000 hours for thermal aging and 2 500 hours for thermo-oxidative aging. Characterization after aging put in evidence the degradation of the material, the damages being more important for the samples aged under oxidative atmosphere.

Mass measurements show a continuous weight loss for all aging temperatures and environments. As expected, weight loss increases with temperature and is more important under oxidative atmosphere than under nitrogen. Moreover, the multi-holed composite loses more weight than the plain one (Fig.6). It can be observed that the resin weight loss is greater than that of composites but it must be reminded that laminates only contain about 40 % resin and the fibers are not concerned with aging at these temperatures.

Figure 6 : Weight losses at 180°C versus aging time : in air (dotted line) and nitrogen (without line)
 ▲ : plain composite ■ : multi-holed composite ◆ : neat resin

FTIR spectra shows the same changes as those observed after aging at 210°C. The most characteristic feature is the disappearance of the 1515-cm⁻¹ peak associated with aromatic groups. The changes are the same for all the aging temperatures, the modifications being faster for higher temperatures. Oxidative atmosphere does not seem to have any influence on the chemical modifications undergone in the oxidized layer.

Figure 7 : FTIR spectra of the composite matrix, initial (plain line) and aged for 2 500 hours at 180°C (dotted line)

Apparition of transverse cracks on free surfaces can be noticed after 500 hours of aging at 180°C in air. At 140°C and 160°C, these cracks appear later. Cracks are also present on the

hole edges. The oxidized layer can be easily observed on the free surface and around holes. This layer appears brighter than the rest of the composite (light area in Fig.8-Left). The oxidized layer width varies with the ply orientation since oxygen can penetrate more deeply when fibers are perpendicular than when they are parallel to the surface. When a crack appears between two plies or within a ply, oxygen diffuses more easily inside the material. On the contrary, laminates aged under inert atmosphere do not exhibit cracks on the free surface or around the holes.

*Figure 8 : Optical micrograph of the laminate aged 1000 hours at 180°C in air
Left : Oxidized layer (light area everywhere on the top of the micrograph) around a hole
Right : Transverse crack on the free surface*

DISCUSSION

As a general rule, accelerated tests are carried out at different temperatures within the glassy state but above the maximal use temperature. Usually, aging tests are realized with higher and higher isotherms. Here, methodology was reversed. First, to emphasize aging effects due to temperature and oxygen, thermal tests were carried out on composites and neat resin at the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin, i.e. 210°C. Then, lower isotherms have been imposed from 180°C down to 140°C in order to cover a range of accelerated aging conditions able to meet the problem of durability and reliability of the composite system.

Damage analysis after aging at T_g

i) Under neutral environmental conditions, only thermal effect is concerned.

On neat resin, temperature leads to some damage which is a consequence coming from chemical and physical aging undergone in the macromolecular network. Physical aging changes the space organization of polymers while chemical aging modifies the backbone by cutting of molecular chains or by cross-linking. Thermolysis effect acts on the structure with weight loss but no cracks at macroscale (laminate scale).

On the composite system, the same effects are observed in the organic matrix as the ones from the neat resin. But, in addition, there are thermal stresses induced by different expansion coefficients between matrix and fibers. These thermal stresses give rise to mechanical stresses responsible for breaking in the matrix and therefore some damage of the composite laminate.

ii) Under oxidizing environmental conditions, we are dealing with a combination of temperature and oxygen effects.

On neat resin, weight loss and degradation are substantial. Weight decreases by removal of volatile products due to both thermo-oxidation and thermolysis. Moreover, thermo-oxidizing effects lead to a very important dimensional shrinkage and surface ablation. Shrinkage is a general phenomenon for all polymers at high temperature. This compaction generates a gradual stress state from the free surface towards the core of the material and the oxidized surface layer appears stiffer than the internal part. However, the combined effects due to stress state, stiffness and specific morphology caused by ablation do not lead to microcracking of the free surfaces after aging at 210°C during 700 hours. On much longer term, it is possible that this combination could give microcracking of the oxidized layer.

On the composite system, the matrix undergoes the same effects as neat resin. Like under neutral environment, thermal stresses have to be highlighted. In the bulk of the composite, there exist thermal stresses from differential expansion between fibers and matrix. But, inside the oxidized matrix layer, these stresses add to stresses coming from shrinkage [9]. The tensile stresses due to shrinkage are more important than those observed in neat resin since the matrix is bonded to the fibers. If the fiber/matrix bonding is strong then microcracking appears in the matrix or around the fiber/matrix interface. If bonding is weak, failure occurs at the interface [10]. However, although stresses from shrinkage are higher in the matrix than in neat resin, they look less important than those implicated in the expansion effect. Besides, composites aged under neutral or oxidizing conditions present some equivalent damage.

In short, at the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin, whatever neutral or oxidizing atmosphere is, the composite system is substantially damaged (cracks, blowing up, delamination). This degradation is primarily due to the stresses from the differential expansion between fibers and matrix. This predominant effect masks thermo-oxidation and thermolysis effects.

Damage analysis after aging below T_g

The aging analysis has been performed by accelerated artificial thermal tests within an hypothesis on equivalence of damage between high temperature/short time and low temperature/long time. However, there is a risk for this equivalence since degradation mechanisms, kinetics, interaction with other aging parameters can be modified. Also, this risk exists between degradation effects at T_g and the ones from lower temperatures. In spite of that, one can estimate that all phenomena and mechanisms of degradation particularly highlighted after aging at T_g are also present for lower temperatures. However, for lower and lower isothermal conditions, each thermal aging gives a relevant damage.

When applied isotherms are lower, differential expansion between fibers and matrix is increasingly small. At 180°C, thermal stresses can still cause microcracking after a few thousand hours, in particular on free edges of composites. On the contrary, at 140°C, no cracks appear in the same aging time. Concerning microcracking at 180°C in air, which part is due to stresses from differential expansion and which part is due to stresses from oxidation ? This problem is still not resolved. However, it is possible to distinguish these relevant damages by deduction from thermal aging under neutral or oxidizing atmosphere. This examination is feasible because the oxidized volume content next to free surfaces is substantial since the composite laminates are multi-holed.

Experimental data show that degradation factors of the composites aged at 180°C for a few thousand hours are almost identified. Structural modifications shown by IR spectra, weight loss and microcracking observed by light microscopy are significant results highlighting the thermo-oxidizing effects in air by comparison with the ones obtained under neutral

environment. As a remarkable result, weight loss is more important for multi-holed than for plain composite. This phenomenon is caused by the greater surface exposed to oxygen for the perforated laminate and emphasizes the interest of this composite system in thermo-oxidative studies.

On the other hand, we know that the oxidized layer is thicker when aging temperature is lower [11]. Moreover, envisaged determination of residual mechanical properties will be complementary data to understand damage of the composite laminates. By step-by-step identification, we would like to separate the degradation mechanisms due to thermal-expansion, thermo-oxidation and thermolysis effects for each imposed isotherm. This investigation is still in progress.

PART CONCLUSION

Damage for aerospace applications in service-life concerns primarily temperature and oxidizing atmosphere. Thermal aging produces some visible and non-visible damage at ply and molecular scales respectively by cracking and network modification.

Due to the different thermal expansion between fibers and matrix, a stress state takes place in the bulk of the composite particularly highlighted at high temperatures. Thermo-oxidation concerns the free surfaces in which are generated gradual stress states within oxidized layers. The holes present all over the surface of the perforated composite enhance the effects of degradation by oxygen, allowing a better comprehension of thermo-oxidation mechanisms. Both, thermal expansion and thermo-oxidation are responsible for some visible damage. When an isotherm increases towards T_g , the former is predominant for cracking and delamination while the latter is major for degradation by weight loss. Hopefully, by studying the multi-holed laminate, it will be possible to determine what is the most degrading parameter between use temperature and oxygen and in which proportion. The non-negligible thermolysis effects concern the whole matrix which gives some non-visible damage (chain cutting) and acts on weight loss too.

A great quantity of work has been achieved. To complete this investigation, mechanical testing will also be conducted to establish the relationships between the degradation mechanisms and the decrease in residual mechanical properties. The difficulty is to link all physico-chemical-mechanical aspects from various aging factors. This task is complex but some proposals are beginning to take form little by little.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Hurel-Hispano (Snecma Group, France), Région Haute-Normandie (France) and the European Fund for Regional Development (FEDER).

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